

Valuing Tradition and Transformation: Envisioning a Myanmar Approach to Educational Assessment in the Age of AI

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ABSTRACT

The spectre of artificial intelligence nullifying the efficacy of traditional methods of academic assessment in 21st century Myanmar presents us with, if the reader will indulge an old proverb, a case of ‘let the snake live, and keep the stick unbroken’ (မြွေမသေ တုတ်မကျိုး).

That is to say, the unexpected November 2022 arrival of ChatGPT (to say nothing of the progeny such rapidly evolving AI systems will likely spawn) is at this very moment spreading like an intellectual pandemic through schools all across the Golden Land—whether our rank and file teachers wish to acknowledge its presence or not.

As a community dedicated to thoughtful education, this new technology compels us to choose between three entirely distinct strategies:

1. Ignore the impact of large language models on learning and assessment altogether and watch our students’ skills erode—the default non-response if we fail to act; or
2. Fight against the inevitable incursion of cut-and-paste technologies such as ChatGPT by categorising them as forms of plagiarism, banning their use in academia, and trying to identify their offspring so we can apply largely feckless punishments as imagined remedies; or
3. Embrace the new technologies and harness them in ways that radically recast Myanmar’s core educational and assessment practises, making them more suitable for the world in which we actually live.

This paper imagines a Myanmar that chooses the third way.

By contextualising such technological advances as useful tools that can decolonise our ailing education system, we imagine new evidence-based teaching and assessment strategies that might challenge our students to achieve higher academic standards, while at the same time allowing our nation to regain control of its own culture, saving it from the enticing clutches of globalisation by creating a truly impactful ‘Myanmar way’ of education for future generations to come.

The opportunity, this paper argues, is for Myanmar’s educational system to ‘go beyond the unknown to meet the known’ (မသိသူ့ကျော်သွား သိသူ့ဖော်စား).

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CHAPTER ONE

What is AI? And why did it suddenly become so popular?

Let us dispense immediately with the incorrect and rather pedestrian understanding that artificial intelligence (or AI) is simply a faster or more intelligent way of computing—better algorithms and all that, so to speak. This characterisation of AI is inaccurate (Emmert-Streib 2020).

Indeed, AI is not simply smarter or even just faster computing (Hagendorff 2020). AI is, rather, the implementation of an entirely new paradigm about how to use, analyse, then come to relatively logical decisions with data (Zhu 2020). A brief review of the history of AI should suffice to make this clear.

Let your mind travel backward, if you will, to our world a mere six and one-half years ago. The year is, I ask you to imagine, 2017.

Whilst Myanmar was in the middle of arguing with the outside world about the challenges we were facing in Rakhine State (Chan 2017), a very different sort of challenge was unfolding in China. This second challenge centred around a game of Go, the ancient Chinese board game of strategy.

The competition pitted a relatively unknown computer programme called AlphaGo created in a laboratory now owned by Google against the quite famous Chinese world champion of Go named Mr Ke Jie [柯洁]. To everyone's great surprise, AlphaGo won the first two games, and Mr Ke Jie surrendered in the third (Chao 2018).

Within two months the Chinese Communist Party (the CCP) issued a directive promising China would become the number one investor in AI no later than the year 2030 (Lee 2018).

It did not, however, require China, it is my rather alarming duty to report, to toil away the 13 years it had allocated to become the largest investor and user of AI in the world. It took only a mere six months (Sköld 2021).

So with China and the United States competing at such a massive scale to create, deploy, and control AI, the race was on (Cave 2019). And it was inevitable that we, mere mortals, would at least be able to dine on at least a few of the crumbs that fell from the tables of government and large industry (Widder 2023).

ChatGPT is one of those crumbs (Kashyap 2023).

But wait! We do an injustice if we simply recount the historical record alone. We must also, to achieve a clear enough understanding, take stock of the technologies involved (Li 2023). After all, if AI and its various children like ChatGPT were such great ideas, why had we not thought of them before (Ray 2023)?

Here the story becomes quite interesting.

In the wake of World War II, computers became of great interest to governments wishing to avoid—or if not to avoid, then at least to win—future wars (Hughes 2011). Universities, militaries, and commercial firms all poured vast amounts of time and money into the development of computers and their programming, hoping to apply them to all aspects of our lives (Ó Riain 2006).

The first great idea with computers—particularly in the days of large mainframe computers which ruled the roost from about 1950 until the introduction of personal desktop computer in the late 1970s—was that the way computers ought to work would be to use a 'rules-based' approach (Cortada 2016). In other words, what some programmers called 'expert systems,' or alternatively 'symbolic systems,' since it normally used binary digits to store its code (Liu 2016).

Simply stated, this meant that all a human had to do was programme the computer to follow a strict set of rules. 'If you see X, then you should do Y' (Lomborg 2020). That sort of thing. And voila! The age of personal computing was born (Campbell-Kelly 2023).

In many ways, this seemed like quite a smart idea. Computers were, after all, faster (and more obedient) than humans when doing things like making calculations or following complex sets of rules (Schuetz 2020).

But of course, this rules-based scheme also had its limitations. It would, for example, only ever be as good as the human beings had programmed it to be, most obviously. Therefore, if the humans could not figure out how to do something, the computer would not be able to be programmed to figure it out either (Confalonieri 2021).

Now some scientists, as far back as the 1950s had begun to question this idea. For one thing, no matter what Science Fiction comics said, technology following human-made rules would likely never become smarter than its homo sapien masters (Wolf-Meyer 2019). It could only be faster, and perhaps register fewer complaints (Diamandis 2020).

But a deeper criticism came about also. And that was that the rules-based approach was not really reflective of how human beings' minds worked anyway (Petrovici 2023).

Except for a small minority of thinkers, most human beings do not generally memorise facts and figures or adhere to rules by arranging them hierarchically, as a computer might store documents in a folder tree, or as a PowerPoint might try to represent ideas arranged as bullet points (Fuster 2022). In fact, humans are (as Buddha frequently pointed out) in many ways naturally averse to following rules (Changeux 2021).

Human thinking, it turns out, is more akin to creating a mental mind map than drafting a list of bullet points (Ganiev 2021). We understand and remember things by discovering patterns in them. We instinctively try to figure out where new ideas and experiences we come across might fit with old ones we already know. Sometimes we even notice patterns that aren't really

there (Gauriot 2019). Then we connect everything we've seen and experienced and thought about by noting the associations each has with the others. Consequently, new ideas are easier to understand and recall in this way (Staresina 2019).

This mind mapping, incidentally, is almost identical to the precise way in which our neurons interconnect over synaptic pathways inside the physical human brain (Sbaa 2020). That seems to be why the method works so well for so many people.

This sort of connective thinking, neurologists tell us, might be called a 'neural network' (Schwarzschild 2023). Simply put, we look at lots of examples of things (what programmers might call 'data') then connect them together as we identify patterns (Farahani 2019).

This is why you may on occasion feel frustrated while trying to recall a word you are certain know quite well but nevertheless cannot quite produce at the moment. You may know, for example, the word you wish to recall (your 'target'). You may feel fairly certain it starts with a particular letter you can identify for example (its 'structure'). You might even be able to think of a number of synonyms for the word (its 'meaning'). Exasperatingly, however, in a number of cases you cannot seem to recall the specific word itself (Futrell 2020).

Now if, on the other hand, humans used a hierarchical rules-based system like the normal desktop computer does, you would be able to simply open an imaginary file cabinet drawer in your mind and pull the word out on command based on any of the criteria you know about the word (Guzman 2020).

But that's not how human minds work (Mercer 2022). We aren't very good at keeping information stored hierarchically, in spite of attempting diligently throughout our school years to do so (Scheerens 2016).

Because our brains use this curious mixture of pattern identification, making connections between things, and sometimes even guessing via intuition, we go about recalling, understanding, and thinking in an entirely different way than computers do—and often obtain different (sometimes rather creative) results (Elder 2019).

So a number of computer scientists in America and the UK back in the 1950s thought, 'Let's try to make a computer that thinks more like a human does — one that simply looks at all the data available to it, defines patterns as best it can, then guesses the ideal way to reach a particular goal given whatever information it can access' (Smith 2017). The idea seemed perfectly sound. And it still does.

But taking on this new more human way of thinking with a computer was not practical half a century ago.

For one thing, we didn't have strong enough computers. We lacked sufficient computing power (Allen 2020).

It is worth noting that the mobile phone you hold in your hands or purse today has far greater speed and significantly more

computing power (Meyer 2019) than all the US government computers NASA used to put a man on the moon in 1969 (Fishman 2020). So without fast enough processors and large enough memory banks, we just couldn't make the neural network approach work, even if we could figure out how to programme it properly.

The second problem, equal in severity to the first, was that until about 2010 we lacked sufficient data for a computer to examine, so that it could search for meaningful patterns from which to make a reasonable guess anyway (Anaby-Tavor 2020).

So we had not one, but two impediments to overcome before we could put this idea of neural networks to the test with computers to find out whether we could ever realise the dream of artificial intelligence after all (Mitchell 2021).

A practical example should suffice to explain what this difference in computing styles would mean:

Let's say we wanted our traditional rules-based computer to identify a cat by looking at a photograph. Not very useful, perhaps. But it should be achievable. So how could we accomplish that? Well, first of all, we would have to teach the computer what a cat is — I mean, what it looks like.

'Computer,' we might say using some complicated language like C# or Python, 'if you identify in the photograph I am going to show you a figure which contains all of the following features, you are to tell us you have identified a cat. Okay?'

'All right,' replies the computer. 'What are the features I should look for?'

Then you, the programmer, would need to enter a list of features that explains what a cat looks like.

'It has a round face,' you might begin, 'and four legs. It has a tail, only one. And it has two eyes on the front of its face.' On and on you would continue until you had exhausted all the patterns you ordinarily think of when identifying a cat yourself. 'It has two ears atop its head, and they are both shaped like triangles. It has a nose, and whiskers.' And so on, and so forth.

Finally, you would show the computer your photograph with a cat in it, and the computer would dutifully search for the features you had described: something with a round face, two eyes, triangular shaped ears, et cetera. Once the computer had identified an object in the photograph with all those features, it would report back to you, 'Ah ha! Here is the cat. I found it!' The whole process would take only a couple of seconds. And most of the time, the computer's findings would be correct (Denning 2019).

So far so good.

But there was a problem with this rule-based method (Boom 2022). And that is that cats do not always look the same in photographs (let alone in real life).

Some cats are skinny, others fat. Some are brown or grey, while others may be black or white in colour. There are short-haired and long-haired cats. Contented and grumpy cats. Some might be lying on their backs upside down in a picture. Or have their hind end facing the camera. Others might appear blurry or stretched out because they are in rapid motion.

Oh dear. This could become difficult.

How could the rules we provide a computer account for the myriad of possibilities in which a cat might present itself — or indeed, through which it may try to camouflage itself? The rules-based approach was simply not robust enough to do us much good when it came to applying computers to such real world problems.

Then came the Internet (Kergel 2020), and along with it, social media (Ortiz-Ospina 2023). And that changed everything (Firth 2019).

Almost overnight, we had access to billions of terabytes of free unstructured data (Abkenar 2021). Everyone seemed to be sharing everything with near abandon (Brammer 2022).

Whereas one might have been able to gather a paltry one or two thousand cat pictures, for example, in the year 2000, computer scientists could now scrape hundreds of millions of cat pictures off the Internet in nanoseconds (especially from people's social media postings) then simply show them all at once to a computer for analysis (Altobelli 2021).

Suddenly, the neural network approach made lots of sense. Our computers had grown much stronger and faster than they had in the past. And we now had a seemingly infinite supply of real world data which we could feed to the computer programme so it could identify its own patterns and connections — even ones that might be difficult for any human to see (Booch 2021).

The age of AI had come upon us (Iansiti 2020).

CHAPTER TWO

Where did the Myanmar educational system come from? And how effective is it, really?

Now, before we plunge into the Myanmar educational system, you may well be asking yourself (and you could hardly be blamed you for doing so) why would anyone wish to find cats?

The answer is simple, and it has little to do with our feline friends. Cats may not be important to identify. Cats are, after all, just cats.

But if you can identify a cat in random photograph, perhaps you might also be able to identify the location of a dangerous

land mine from a satellite image (Pryshchenko 2022). Or a tumour from an x-ray (Jiang 2020). Or the maximum price a customer might be willing to pay in a particular financial transaction (Belanche 2019).

And if this new capability could be applied to security, healthcare, and finance, perhaps it might have implications for education as well (Chen 2020).

So with that opportunity in mind, let us turn our attention now squarely on to the Myanmar educational system itself.

From 1948 until about 1965, among the highest ranked educational systems in Asia (Yukimoto 2021), Myanmar's schooling has, it seems, in recent years fallen upon hard times (Shah 2019).

Whereas Myanmar used to rank in the top ten for Asia (Hays 2014) and even boasted the highest local-language literacy rate in the British empire (Lorch 2007), Myanmar currently ranks a distressing 136th out of 154 nations in educational outcomes according to the Global Knowledge Index (Steiner 2022).

Even high-school matriculation rates appear disastrous, whether considered in isolation, or when compared with regional neighbours as seen in the chart below.

According to most recent figures, only 22% of eligible high-school aged children matriculate at all — nearly two times worse than Thailand — leaving an astonishing failure rate of some 88% (Mitchell 2019).

Many educators of course, however, believe that with proper reforms, Myanmar can achieve a marked turnaround in outcomes (Kandiko 2020).

Undisciplined use of ChatGPT by Myanmar students, however, is unlikely to bring that about (Sok 2023).

The most obvious problem seems that students may use it as an even lower effort system of plagiarism, simply asking ChatGPT to write essays for them and so on, which ChatGPT is very capable of doing almost instantly (Dien 2023). In such cases, students are unlikely to learn anything, as now they have a cyber-brother who can painlessly do all their work for them. In such a scenario, learning is likely to nearly cease (Gregorcic 2023).

Corollary to this first drawback, comes the even deeper problem that ChatGPT is based on a Large Language Model (LLM), not upon thinking and decision-making as you and I understand it (Schneider 2023).

Just as an AI model can identify a cat, a landmine, or a tumour without really knowing what any of those things are, what it's doing, or why, so can a LLM like ChatGPT tell a person what they most want to hear by drawing upon the corpus of as much accessible language as it can locate on the Internet, then selecting the statistically most-likely words that would follow such a query (Chomsky 2023).

A significant problem with this approach is that ChatGPT's response may at times simply be wrong. It may, for example, represent the statistically most prevalent view from the language sets it draws from, but not necessarily the correct one (Farrokhnia 2023). Certainly, it is more likely to choose the majority view from its language dataset than it is to parse the ethics of its answer in the context the questioner may be considering (Blum 2022).

Statistics is a powerful thing. But it cannot do everything well (Nakkiran 2021).

Statistically speaking, for example, if democracy prevailed around the world in a unified form, Buddhism as a minority religion would most likely be voted out of existence (Oyekan 2020). Buddhism is, after all, a minority religion with a smaller number of adherents than, say, Christianity, or Islam, or Hinduism (Inglehart 2020). Yet, there are still plenty of people who believe Buddhism is an important framework to guide our daily life choices (for some of us, the most important framework), even if it does not statistically attract the most followers (Collins 2020).

So we face two problems in Myanmar as our students begin adopting ChatGPT willy-nilly. First, they may cease to learn anything because the machine is doing all their thinking for them (Yu 2023). And second, the machine (whether intentionally or not) may lead the students' thinking such as it is inextricably toward a general malaise of globalised thinking that does almost nothing to account for Myanmar's particular culture, values, or unique goals (Olssen 2020).

Already, we are labouring under the shadow of a post-colonial system of education — a method of schooling and assessment designed by the British more than a century ago and intended for nothing more than to keep the queen's subjects in line (Suante 2022). Note, if you will, that neither Cambridge nor Oxford in England keep to this old-fashioned system of teaching and learning (Smith 2021). Only the former colonies do so (Dlamini 2019).

We must accept that the colonial system of education forced upon our country more than a century ago was the very essence of the master-slave relationship (Duke 2020). It was intended to create obedience, not learning; conformity, not problem solving (Topdar 2020). And it may be time for us to reinvent the way we teach and assess in Myanmar.

Perhaps, as I will claim in this paper's third chapter to follow, the appearance of ChatGPT can give us the push we need to completely modernise and localise our education system (Barua 2022), to make a more effective Myanmar education process support our own precious culture, teach our own values, and revel in our own languages (Banerjee 2023).

Dare I say, the appearance of AI may provide a chance for both the Ministry of Education and local teachers to de-colonise Myanmar's education system once and for all?

CHAPTER THREE

What more efficient options might Myanmar use for assessment in the age of AI?

Thus having, I hope, satisfactorily established that (1) the current Myanmar education system remains dysfunctional, and (2) that the sudden introduction of AI technologies such as ChatGPT (and its probable progeny) are likely to make things worse if we ignore them, let us set ourselves to the vital task of describing precisely how this situation might be used to trigger a more effective, truly inclusive Myanmar system of evidence-based education that can put our nation back on top.

TEACHING METHODS

To set the process in motion, research suggests we must decolonise our teaching methods by replacing antiquated colonial era rote-memorisation strategies with teaching strategies whose efficacy is supported by evidence-based research and which promote critical thinking in the context of Myanmar maintaining its own culture.

Specifically, to promote more 'active thinking' we could employ from kindergarten through graduate schools such in-class strategies as:

1. **Socratic Questioning:** Encouraging critical thinking through open-ended questions and discussions (Chew 2019).
2. **Think-Pair-Share:** Students think individually, discuss in pairs, and then afterward share their thoughts with the class (Silva 2022).
3. **Jigsaw Method:** Divide students into expert groups to study a specific topic, then reassemble them so they can share their knowledge with their peers (Drouet 2023).
4. **Gamification:** Incorporate game elements into study to make learning more engaging (Manzano-León 2021).
5. **Flipped Classroom:** Assigning video lectures as homework, reserving class time for active learning (Galindo-Dominguez 2021).

Then to reduce dropouts from students who fall behind, 'differentiate learning' by using the following well-known teaching methods:

6. **Multiple Learning Stations:** Create different activity stations to cater to various learning styles and sub-topics (Fu 2023).
7. **Tiered Assignments:** Offer assignments with varying levels of complexity (Onyishi 2020).
8. **Flexible Grouping:** Adapt groups dynamically based on students' needs and abilities for each day's lesson (Colón 2022).

To assure our teaching does not simply parrot foreign texts, but rather incorporates native Myanmar cultures such as Bamar, Shan (including Tai Yai, Tai Lü, Tai Khuen, Tai Nüa and so forth), Karen, Mon, Kayah, Rakhine, and Kachin, among others, we could deploy the following 'culturally responsive teaching' strategies:

9. **Culturally Relevant Materials:** Integrate local literature, art, and resources from diverse backgrounds (Abacioglu 2020).
10. **Cultural Identity Exploration:** Encourage students to explore their cultural identity and share their family's experiences (Verhoeven 2019).
11. **Inclusive Language:** Use language that respects and includes diverse backgrounds and identities (Krulatz 2020), including local languages and dialects in addition to Burmese or English (Myo 2021).

Because our graduates will need to interact with the larger world around them, we might also include 'technology integration' into our teaching strategies to the extent possible by using such low-cost activities as:

12. **Educational Apps:** Use mobile phone apps or Internet apps to expand interactive lessons and practice (Papadakis 2021).
13. **Interactive Whiteboards:** If available, utilize interactive whiteboards to create dynamic and visual lessons (Shi 2019). However, it should be noted that a school that cannot afford an interactive whiteboard can still simulate a very similar experience on a traditional chalk board.
14. **Online Discussion Boards:** Foster online discussions for extended learning through such free resources as Google Classroom, Google Jamboard, or Moodle (Delaney 2019).
15. **Video Conferencing:** Connect with experts or students from different regions of Myanmar or even other countries via Zoom (or Microsoft Teams) to create live learning experiences previously not possible (Gladović 2020).

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Equally important to decolonising teaching methods, the presence of AI and the threat that students may, if left to their

own devices, use such new technologies to weaken rather than strengthen their academic skills, demands our assessment methods also adapt to the changing paradigm.

Rather than ban ChatGPT, however, we can teach students how to use it as if it were a private tutor, available for them at all hours. But we must then create novel ways to integrate our more robust teaching strategies with cleverer assessment methods more impervious to fakery by ChatGPT.

Such revised 'assessment methods' appropriate for the age of AI might include the following:

1. **Graded In-Class Discussions for Socratic Seminars:** Encourage students to engage in thoughtful, open-ended discussions about the course material (Legath 2023). This helps students assess their ability to analyse, synthesize, and articulate complex thoughts (Dalke 2023).
2. **Oral Presentations:** Require students to present their research or findings in front of the class (Lin 2023). This assesses their ability to convey their knowledge verbally, which is often more challenging than writing (Durán-Heras 2023).
3. **Peer Review and Feedback:** Have students review and critique each other's work (Alqassab 2023). This encourages critical thinking and peer-to-peer learning (Panadero 2023).
4. **Problem-Solving Exercises:** Create assignments that require students to apply their knowledge to real-world problems (Jha 2023). Assess their problem-solving skills and their ability to adapt course material to practical situations (Duyver 2023).
5. **Case Studies, Written or Spoken:** Assign case studies (Perkins 2023) that demand a deep understanding of the subject matter and the ability to apply concepts to complex, real-world scenarios (Schillings 2023).
6. **Concept Maps and Mind Maps:** Ask students to create visual representations of their understanding of the subject (Fernández 2022), showcasing the relationships between key concepts (Ivanova 2023).
7. **Collaborative Projects:** Assign group projects that require human teamwork (Rojo 2023), research, and the synthesis of knowledge to create a final product (Olasina 2023).
8. **Essay Questions with a Twist:** If you still want to use written assessments, pose essay questions that require students to apply critical thinking and analysis (Dobson 2023) rather than regurgitating facts (Abirami 2023).
9. **Open-Book Exams without Computer Access:** Instead of traditional closed-book exams, or papers to be written on computers at home, allow students to use their textbooks

or class notes to take live exams in class (Roberts 2023). This shifts the focus from memorization to comprehension and application (Flanagan 2023).

10. **Portfolio Assessment:** Have students maintain a portfolio of their work throughout the semester, including drafts, revisions, and reflections (Harizon 2023). This demonstrates their progress and learning journey (Tong 2023).
11. **Authentic Assessments:** Design assessments that mirror real-world tasks and challenges in the field (Gedera 2023), so students are tested on their ability to use knowledge in practical situations (Nuryani 2023).
12. **Mentorship and Conferencing:** Meet with students individually to discuss their work, progress, and understanding of the material (Packard 2023). This personal interaction can reveal a lot about their comprehension (Crawford 2023).
13. **Online Quizzes with Conceptual Questions:** If you must use online quizzes, ensure that questions require students to understand concepts and apply knowledge (Suhonen 2023) rather than merely looking up answers (Tibrani 2023).
14. **Creative Projects:** Encourage students to create (Hu 2023) multimedia presentations, videos, artwork, or other creative outputs related to the subject matter (Ostrovskaya 2023).
15. **Reflection Papers:** Ask students to write reflection papers on what they've learned, how it connects to the real world (Marquez 2023), and how they've grown in their understanding (Hammar 2023).
16. **Capstone Projects:** At the college level, consider capstone projects that require students to demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of their major (Millet 2023) through a substantial research or creative project (Krsmanovic 2023).
17. **Peer Teaching:** Allow students to teach a portion of the class or lead a discussion on a particular topic (Gurbanov 2023). This shows not only their knowledge but their ability to communicate it effectively (Gupta 2023).
18. **In-Class Quizzes:** Periodic quizzes can help gauge students' understanding of recent material (Kim 2023) and reinforce active learning (Gedera 2023).

DISCUSSION

The spectre of artificial intelligence nullifying the efficacy of traditional methods of academic assessment placed educators in Myanmar at an unexpected crossroads. In response, we can either

1. Ignore the impact of large language models on learning and assessment altogether and watch our students' skills erode; or
2. Fight against the inevitable incursion of technologies such as ChatGPT by categorising them as forms of plagiarism; or
3. Embrace the new technologies and harness them in ways that radically recast Myanmar's core educational and assessment practises, making them more suitable for the world in which we actually live.

This paper has proposed Myanmar take on the third way. And in doing so, the paper has provided 15 distinct evidence-based methods of teaching, and 18 distinct evidence-based methods of assessment that counteract the likelihood that students will be tempted (or able) to cheat using such programmes as ChatGPT.

By contextualising such technological advances as useful tools that can decolonise our ailing education system, we have together imagined a new path forward that can not only achieve higher academic standards, but also support our nation in strengthening its own indigenous cultures and ways of being, thereby saving Myanmar from fate suffered by so many other post-colonial countries who unthinkingly embrace a new form of colonialism, 'globalisation,' rather than truly valuing both tradition and transformation to find their own way.

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The author declares he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

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This research was conducted with approval from the Research Ethics Committee of International Leadership University in Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar: Approval number 2023/ 2270154.

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